

ISSN(E): 2770-8125

EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL OF ADVANCED
RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

EIJARI

2026

www.innojournals.my.id/index.php/eijari

European International Journal of Advanced Research and Innovations

Volume 02, Issue 06

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Professor Emma Franke

Editor in Chief

Prof. Jo Coldwell-Neilson

Associate Editor In Chief Deakin University, Australia

Mr Mohd Helmy

Abd Wahab Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia

Shafi'i Muhammad Abdulhamid

Federal University Of Technology Minna, Nigeria., Nigeria

Dr Man Fung (Kelvin) Lo

The Chinese University Of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

Dr Ahmad Samed

Al-Adwan Al Ahliyya Amman University, Jordan

Waleed Alsabhan

Kacst, Saudi Arabia Yvonne Antonucci Widener University, United States

Prof. Orit Avidov Ungar

Achva Academic College & Open University Of Israel, Israel

Dr. Aslina Baharum

Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia

COOPERATION OF SOCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE FIGHT AGAINST DRUG ADDICTION

Makhsudova Holiskhon Ummatovna

Andijan State technical Institute

Docent of the Department of Languages and Humanities

PhD on Philology

Email: xolisxon0408@gmail.com

Phone: +998911606100

Abstract. This article analyzes the role of social institutions and their mutual cooperation in combating drug addiction. The negative impact of drug addiction on social development, youth education, and public health is highlighted, and the effectiveness of the joint activities of the family, educational institutions, neighborhood, law enforcement agencies, the health system, and public organizations is revealed. According to the results of the study, the success of the fight against drug addiction depends on the integral cooperation of all social institutions.

Keywords: drug addiction, social institutions, cooperation, prevention, youth, family, neighborhood, education, healthy lifestyle.

I. INTRODUCTION. One of the most pressing social problems facing human development in the 21st century is drug addiction. This negative vice not only harms the physical and mental health of an individual, but also poses a serious threat to the spiritual and moral environment, economic development and social stability of society⁷. Drug addiction leads to such negative situations as crime, family breakdown, and unemployment, an increase in various diseases and a decrease in social activity among young people. Therefore, in many countries of the world, the fight against the illegal trafficking and consumption of drugs is recognized as one of the priority areas of state policy.

Globalization processes, the rapid development of information and communication technologies, and the expansion of international migration flows are creating new opportunities for the illegal distribution of drugs. In particular, the increasing number of cases of promotion and distribution of drugs through Internet networks and social platforms threatens the safety of young people⁸. The insufficiently formed life experience of young people and their rapid exposure to various negative influences are contributing to the further exacerbation of the problem of drug addiction.

Preventing and combating drug addiction is not the sole responsibility of law enforcement agencies or the health care system. This problem is a multifaceted social phenomenon, and effective combating it requires the joint work of all social

⁷ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2023.

⁸ United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. *World Drug Report 2024*. – Vienna, 2024.

institutions in society. Social institutions include the family, educational institutions, the neighborhood, the health care system, law enforcement agencies, the media, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and youth organizations. Each of these institutions performs its own tasks in drug prevention, and their mutual cooperation significantly increases the effectiveness of preventive work. The family, as the main place for raising children, forms a healthy worldview in young people, while educational institutions provide them with the necessary knowledge and skills. Mahalla citizen assemblies carry out social control and spiritual and educational activities by working directly with the population. While law enforcement agencies combat the illegal trafficking of drugs, health care institutions are engaged in the treatment and rehabilitation of dependent individuals. The media and public organizations are promoting a healthy lifestyle among the population and educating them about the harmful effects of drug abuse.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the issues of protecting young people from various foreign ideas and harmful habits, establishing a healthy lifestyle, and improving the fight against drug addiction. The laws, state programs, and preventive measures adopted in this regard serve to ensure the physical and spiritual well-being of the younger generation. However, the complex social nature of drug addiction requires further strengthening the cooperation of all social institutions in solving this problem⁹.

The purpose of this article is to scientifically analyze the role and tasks of social institutions in the fight against drug addiction, study the mechanisms of their interaction, and develop proposals and recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of preventive work¹⁰. During the study, the theoretical and practical aspects of the fight against drug addiction are covered, and current issues of cooperation between social institutions are analyzed. As a result, scientifically based conclusions are drawn on the formation of a healthy lifestyle in society and the prevention of drug addiction.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. The study used methods of analysis, comparative study, generalization and systematic approach. National and international experiences, regulatory legal acts and scientific literature on the fight against drug addiction were studied.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. During the study, the role of social institutions in the fight against drug addiction and the mechanisms of cooperation between them were analyzed. The results obtained showed that the prevention of drug addiction and effective fight against it are not limited to the activities of any organization or institution¹¹. The complex social nature of this problem requires the cooperation of all social institutions.

⁹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy".

¹⁰ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Strategy of the New Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2021.

¹¹ Karimov I.A. *Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch*. – Toshkent: Ma'naviyat 2008.

The analysis revealed that the most important link in the fight against drug addiction is the family. The presence of a healthy spiritual environment in the family, a responsible approach of parents to raising children are the main factors protecting young people from various harmful vices. Sincere communication between parents and children, mutual trust and the presence of control mechanisms reduce the likelihood of young people succumbing to negative influences.

Observations show that family conflicts, weak control, insufficient pedagogical literacy of parents or socio-economic problems in the family in some cases increase the tendency of young people to use drugs. Therefore, it is important to improve the system of spiritual, educational and psychological work with families.

The results of the study showed that educational institutions are an important subject of drug prevention. Schools, academic lyceums, vocational schools and higher educational institutions play an important role in forming healthy lifestyle skills in the minds of young people, improving legal culture and developing a negative attitude towards harmful habits¹².

Regular roundtable discussions, meetings, seminars, trainings and awareness-raising events held in educational institutions serve to increase the knowledge of students and young people about drug addiction. At the same time, individual work of teachers and psychologists with students allows for early identification of young people belonging to the risk group. This increases the effectiveness of preventive measures¹³.

Neighborhood citizens' assemblies are one of the closest social institutions that work directly with the population in preventing drug addiction. According to the results of the study, the tendency to drug addiction is significantly reduced by meaningfully organizing the leisure time of young people in neighborhoods, organizing sports and cultural events, and supporting families in need of social protection.

As a result of the joint activities of region activists, prevention inspectors, youth leaders and luminaries, preventive control in the regions is being strengthened. In particular, individual work with young people at risk, their orientation to a profession and ensuring their employment are yielding positive results¹⁴.

Analyses show that the activities of law enforcement agencies are of particular importance in the fight against drug addiction. Measures taken by internal affairs bodies, customs services and other authorized structures against the illegal circulation of drugs are helping to reduce the level of drug addiction.

Operational preventive measures carried out by law enforcement agencies, identifying and eliminating illegal trade channels and conducting explanatory work

¹² Karimov I.A. *Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch*. – Toshkent: Ma'naviyat 2008.

¹³ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Citizens' Health".

¹⁴ Ismoilov A., Raximov B. *Yoshlar o'rtasida giyohvandlik profilaktikasi masalalari*. – Toshkent, 2022.

among young people are an important component of the prevention system. However, the effectiveness of these activities directly depends on the level of cooperation with the public.

One of the important areas of the fight against drug addiction is the development of a narcological assistance and rehabilitation system. The study found that timely provision of medical and psychological assistance increases the chances of drug addicts returning to a healthy life.

Preventive examinations, psychological counseling, and rehabilitation programs conducted by health care institutions not only help patients recover, but also help them reintegrate into society. Therefore, it is necessary to further improve the activities of drug treatment services.

The results of the study showed that non-governmental organizations and the media are important actors in the fight against drug addiction. They are actively involved in promoting a healthy lifestyle among different segments of the population, especially young people, raising awareness about the negative consequences of drug addiction, and implementing preventive projects.

Propaganda work carried out through television, radio, Internet publications and social networks allows you to reach a wide audience. The effective use of modern information technologies serves to form new mechanisms for combating drug addiction.

As a result of the analysis, it was determined that the highest results in the fight against drug addiction are observed in areas where there is close cooperation between social institutions. The family-school-neighborhood cooperation model is emerging as the main link in the prevention system. The inclusion of law enforcement agencies, health institutions and public organizations in this model forms a comprehensive preventive system.

Also, information exchange, the organization of joint events, individual work with problematic youth and strengthening public control were assessed as the main factors that increase the effectiveness of cooperation.

In general, the results of the study confirmed that the interrelated and systematic activities of social institutions are important in combating drug addiction, not in isolation. Improving this cooperation will help prevent drug addiction among young people, promote a healthy lifestyle, and strengthen the social stability of society.

IV. CONCLUSION. The results of the study showed that drug addiction is one of the complex social problems that seriously threatens the development of modern society. This vice negatively affects not only human health, but also family relationships, youth education, the spiritual and moral environment of society, and the socio-economic development of the state. Therefore, the issue of combating drug addiction remains one of the priority tasks of state bodies, civil society institutions, and the general public.

During the study, the activities of the family, educational institutions, neighborhoods, law enforcement agencies, the healthcare system, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and the media in combating drug addiction were analyzed. As a result of the analysis, it was found that each of these institutions plays an important role in the prevention system, but the effectiveness of their activities largely depends on the level of interaction.

The family, as a primary social institution that protects young people from harmful habits, is the main link in drug prevention. Educational institutions, on the other hand, are an important subject of preventive work by forming a healthy lifestyle, legal culture and spiritual values in the minds of young people. Mahalla citizens' assemblies, as institutions that have the opportunity to work directly with the population, perform important tasks in providing social support, monitoring and meaningful organization of their free time for young people.

Also, measures taken by law enforcement agencies against the illegal trafficking of drugs are preventing the spread of drug addiction. Treatment and rehabilitation work carried out by health care institutions is helping drug addicts to re-adapt to society. Educational and promotional work carried out by non-governmental non-profit organizations and the media is of great importance in raising awareness of the population about this problem.

In general, the success of the fight against drug addiction depends on the integral cooperation of all social institutions in society, public activity and systematic organization of preventive work. Strengthening this cooperation will help prevent drug addiction among young people, promote a healthy lifestyle, increase social activity of citizens, and ensure the stability of society. Therefore, the development of cooperation between social institutions in the fight against drug addiction remains relevant as one of the important social tasks of today.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2023.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On State Youth Policy”.
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Preservation of Citizens’ Health”.
4. Karimov I.A. Yuksak ma’naviyat – yengilmas kuch. – Toshkent: Ma’naviyat, 2008.
5. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O‘zbekiston strategiyasi. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston, 2021.
6. United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). World Drug Report. – Vienna, 2024.
7. Ismoilov A., Raximov B. Yoshlar o‘rtasida giyohvandlik profilaktikasi masalalari. – Toshkent, 2022